

TECHNOLOGIES AND LEGALITIES OF APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNIQUES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685293>

Annotation. This article analyzes the technologies and legalities of using modern methods in the pre-school education system in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: preschool education, modernity, method, methodology, technology, modern approaches, legalities.

Preschool education is usually grouped into several aspects: physical development (control of the body as to both gross and fine motor functions); perception and sensory development (developing the sensory system); communication and language development; cognitive development (developing all psychophysiological aspects concerning thinking, sensations, emotions etc using for cognitive processes); emotional development (developing and controlling emotions by a child); social development (socialization process, developing child's identity and his relationship with others).

However, the fundamental problem of preschool education lies in that, that pedagogical community does not have a clear idea about the main goal of human development. Revealing this goal, being the system-forming entity for all other goals and aspects of child's development, is the major purpose of this article focusing on unification the mentioned aspects of child's development around this system-forming goal.

The main feature of our world is motion, being the most important attribute of the matter, the fundamental way of its existence. Thus, the major contents and the most essential way of man's existence is motion, development in time and space, the fullest and the most intensive expression of which can be observed in baby and juvenile age, where this development as socio-personal phenomenon is arranged in the processes of teaching, upbringing, education, realized within the framework of school system. That is why the main volume of social and individual life is concentrated in the domain of education which crystallizes the continuous intellectual space of cultural and historic development of mankind. School meets the requirements of society and has always been the basic social institute that, as J. Dewey puts it, can create in the project such type of a society which we would like to realize; influencing the people in this direction, we would gradually change the nature of adult society.

In this case the individual plunges in so-called cognitive dissonance and seeks to free himself from the ambivalent, and therefore paradoxical, cognitive situation through the distortion of reality. So, wanting something and not being able to get this thing, people may resort to discredit this thing (which can be illustrated by the Russian fable about "green grapes"), thus distorting the reality.

The freedom is the main goal of man's development and educational process, around which all other educational aims are to be organized. The realization of freedom as the major developmental goals within the preschool education presupposes the actualization of a new paradigm of preschool education.

So defining this goal and to tying the latter with the major aspects of preschool education can be achieved due to the conclusion that conceptually any educational ideology and its strategy are built on the basis of two major aspects - the goals of education and the ways of its achieving. If a man takes for the purpose of education the moulding of a harmonious personality, he should analyze two problems: the problem of defining a harmonic state, and the problem of forming this state.

From the broad philosophical and psychological standpoint harmony is, first of all, the wholeness, that is, the synthesis of all psychophysiological constituents of a person, the unity of his physical and psychological sides, the state integrating thoughts and actions of their carriers, uniting in one whole all multiple dichotomies of our existence, such as moral and factual, internal and external, individual-personal and socio-historic.

It is clear, that the state of people's harmony, as something integral, is realized within the framework of such entity which, first, is a system-forming factor of a person as a holistic system, and, secondly, plays a role of the main regulator of its behavior. We have every reason to state that such a regulator is actualized on the basis of functions of hemispheres of man's cerebral cortex, about what B. G. Anan'jev wrote as far back as sixties, and what is difficult to dispute nowadays.

As the appropriate investigations show, the hemispheres may be possibly considered a psychophysiological focus of human organism, because with their functions such sides of human entity are related, as mechanisms of aim creation and searching for the ways of aim's achieving, energetic and informational regulation of people's behavior, empathy and reflection, extroversion and introversion, automatic and spontaneous psychic activity, first and second signaling systems, power and weakness of nervous processes, their lability and inertness, irritation and suppression, I and non-I, ergotrophic and trophotropic functions, volitional and non-volitional psychic spheres, sympathetic and parasympathetic branches of vegetative nervous system etc.

Any automatic (subconscious) action of a man is included in right hemispheric, and non-automatic (conscious) - in left hemispheric aspects of psychic activity.

It should be noted that right hemispheric strategy of perception, thinking and mastering the world represents emotional, concrete, expressive, holistic world view which forms ambiguous polysemantic linguistic and motivational context of reflecting the reality, corresponding with energy-field aspect of the Universe which can be characterized as continual type of the matter.

Left hemispheric perception strategy represents, on the contrary, abstract-logical, sign-symbolic, discursive, conceptual, discrete, plural world outlook which forms accurate linguistic and motivational context of reflecting the surrounding world, corresponding with substance-informational aspect of the Universe which can be characterized as discrete type of the matter. We

may add that right hemisphere "creates" religious-mythological, artistic reality, awaking to life such forms of social consciousness, as religion and art. Left hemisphere "creates" scientific-technocratic reality, awaking to life science and politics.

It should be emphasized that in onto- and phylogenesis of a living being one observes the process of gradual increasing the hemispheric asymmetry (in a baby the state of functional symmetry of cerebral cortex is observed when the hemispheres work according to the functional pattern of the right hemisphere), the greatest expression of which is reached at a mature age. Afterwards, the hemispheric asymmetry is gradually leveling.

The condition for functional synthesis of hemispheres is revealing when elderly person, enriched in life experience, factually transforms himself into a child with its plastic psyche, spontaneity, frankness and openness of perception of the world.

Here we have generally known philosophical idea about the development (thesis - antithesis - synthesis) when the third stage of the development dialectically repeats the first one, but on the higher level of development.

If we take into consideration the fact, that right hemispheric functions focus on the present time with turning to the past, and the left one - on the present time with turning to the future, then it is possible to say that person's development moves quite naturally from past to future, and from the latter - to their integration, when spacio-temporal dichotomy of the Being is eliminated and a person liberates himself from "the curses of Chronos".

The method of integration of "right" and "left" types of world comprehension in schooling process is illustrated by the pedagogical system of V. F. Shatalov that has a miraculous effect. This system applies the principle of hemispheric synthesis when in the framework of the schooling process the two polar aspects of psychics (right, concrete and left, abstract) are putting into harmony. Here on the one hand the pupils are given a certain set of concrete facts (of mathematical, geographic, historical nature, etc.), and on the other hand - all these facts are transformed in the language of so called auxiliary signals which are of abstract nature. That is, every fact and the strings of facts are encoded by abstract signs.

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